

ACCURACY OF 3D THERMO-TOMOGRAPHY MODEL FOR THE EVALUATION OF AEROSPACE COMPONENTS

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ABSTRACT

Slowly but surely, more and more automated thermography measurement is being applied in industry. Thermography provides a high sensitivity for most defects, high accuracy in locating defects and mostly used in reflection mode, which is important for complex and large aerospace components. Furthermore, due to focal plane array detector, a large area can be measured comparatively in much less time than ultrasound inspection. By measuring components (< 6 mm thickness) with thermography the load of water coupled ultrasonic machine can be relieved. Recently, for the first time FACC [2] has qualified thermography inspection method for CFRP components and has reduced the inspection time up to 50 %, although measurement is conducted manually. Already in 2012 [1], DLR Augsburg carried out the automated thermography measurement of an aircraft structure and published the results. Since then, both the automated measurement process and the evaluation process have been continuously improved. To reduce the evaluation process time by means of 3D visualisation model for a large number of 2D thermography images, 2 independent methods [3] are developed at DLR. A further development of the evaluation process for both methods occurred first by generating a 3D-thermo-tomography model [4] (Measurement results according to their thermal depth). The defect analysis with this generated model takes place directly in the CAD environment. Along with their development phase accuracy of system components for two methods were analysed [5] within the scope of those respective test series. Moreover, experiments were performed for complete evaluation (the absolute and relative system accuracy between two methods), and 3D thermography models were generated with both methods to analyse visualisation accuracy of 3D model in CAD environment. The results are discussed in this paper.

1 Introduction

Autonomous navigation with NDT systems like Thermography on a large aircraft component (e.g. fuselage sections, wing structures or similar) is a major challenge for standard industry robots [1]. The problem can be basically divided into positioning and path planning. Robot Tool-Centre-Point (TCP) positional accuracy depends mostly on robot pose and their orientation [5]. Many other factors like gravitational or deflecting forces may affect the absolute positional accuracy of robot TCP positions. For example, 0.1 absolute robot inaccuracies (TCP) can cause for 1 meter working distance up to 3 mm positional error. Another major drawback of a Thermography system is that certified examiners evaluate every 2D-Thermography image per measuring field one after one. This unhandy and less intuitive method for large number of numerical data is inappropriate for industrial applications. Full-scale evaluation in 3D components coordinates gives complex but complete 3D error propagation knowledge. To reduce the evaluation process time by means of 3D visualization model for a large number of 2D thermography images, 2 independent methods [3] are developed at DLR. There are plenty of existing methods and technologies for 3D texture mapping like the stereo vision method, using 3D features, or the multi-view method. These methods require either a second camera or time consuming additional processes like several images taken from different views for each single measuring field. In order to calculate 2D-3D camera projection parameters for 3D visualization, the

new method using Thermography camera, which is also used for NDT, and a laser system mounted above the Robotic cell, eliminates the uncertainty of robots position accuracy. Through an easy calibration process, within a few minutes the laser system is calibrated to the component coordinate systems and projects predefined 3D points for every measuring field. These 3D points are captured by the Thermography camera; afterwards a 2D-3D point correspondence algorithm is applied to calculate 2D-3D camera projection parameters. The second Method uses the robot pose and a kinematic-coordinate-relationships algorithm is applied to the images. For both methods single thermal image is captured using a Thermography camera. The first method is suited for research and development as well as for production inspection with or without using a robot for camera positioning while the second method requires a robot. The first method enables also contactless localization of detected defects. Results of the 3D thermo-tomography model of both methods are published in this paper [4]. Furthermore, the geometric and hand-eye calibration proved to be an important building block for the 3D reconstruction of all thermographic images. The topic has already been dealt with at DLR in advance [6], [7]. Matlab Calibration Toolbox was used to perform the geometric calibration (intrinsic parameters) and the necessary process steps were developed from it. This toolbox was extended to execute hand-eye calibration (extrinsic parameters). The accuracy of the hand-eye calibration method and influencing parameters were analyzed[3].

Accuracy, reproducibility and flexibility of both 3D visualization methods are experimentally validated, compared and discussed in this work. The 3D results are imported directly into the CAD environment for further structural analysis.

2 System accuracy evaluation of both 3D visualisation methods

In this work, the above mentioned 3D-thermography methods and associated system components are evaluated by means of determining the absolute and also relative system accuracy. Along with their development phase, both methods were evaluated individually within the scope of those respective test series. In these test series, different carbon fibre components were used which had no distinct reference points for an absolute accuracy check and had fringed edges, so that relative accuracy of 3D results were evaluated with only the help of natural surface anomalies. The robot's absolute accuracy [5], geometric and hand-eye calibration results [3] are major influencing factors for the noticeably lower accuracy of the robot-based 3D model generation method. Preliminary investigations and system validation in [8] showed that the robot's PTP and LIN movement with override, accurate end-effector load data and the robot's motor temperate increment due to its continuous movement are key parameters for system stability. Therefore, for the complete evaluation of systems, robot movements were generated such a way that the robot itself does not cause any additional errors.

2.1 Absolute robot accuracy

To determine absolute robot accuracy without a mounted end-effector at flange, numerous experiments were conducted. Experiment results in [9] have shown that the absolute accuracy decreases with increasing distance from the measured base coordinate. Analysing absolute robot accuracy with the mounted thermography end-effector is more complex than without it. Figure 1 represents the concept for absolute robot accuracy evaluation as well as for hand-eye calibration. The essential element for this experiment is multi-sided probe (MSP), which tracks with a Leica laser tracker and delivers 6D absolute position information instead of the 3D information with T-probe. MSP offer the advantage that the robot position can be measured more easily and precisely than with the T-probe measurement. Figure 2 shows the mounted MSP with the thermography end-effector at the flange. By measuring the reflector position with the laser tracker, the difference between the robot's target and its actual position can be determined. Therefore, a coordinate relationship between the MSP and the laser tracker was created by best-fit transformation, which was performed by using the Robcal program with randomly-chosen 12 taught robot positions and measured MSP reflector positions. Robcal delivers 6D coordinate transformation data first between $MSP_{reflector}$ and F_{flange} and secondly between $R_{rob-root}$ and $L_{laser\ tracker}$. Through repeated experimentation with the actual end-effector's load data a 0.24 best-fit transformation error was ascertained compare to 0.42 without it. The actual load data, which is essential for better absolute accuracy, was determined with the load

detection function provided by KUKA. The smaller error indicates better absolute position accuracy between calculated software data (target position) and actual position data (where the robot is). All this calculated coordinate transformation data was entered in Spatial Analyser for further data acquisition and analysis.

Figure 1: Evaluation concept for hand-eye calibration and absolute robot accuracy

Furthermore Virtual Tip, as a measuring instrument, was configured with Leica Tracker Pilot software. Virtual Tip, which is determined for now in CAD, contains static coordinate transformation data between $MSP_{reflector}$ and TCP_{camera} . This is necessary for determining hand-eye calibration accuracy. After the experimental setup was ready, a small carbon fibre plate was placed in two different positions to determine the robot's absolute accuracy. Base position 2 was selected in ISO-CUBE range to achieve better accuracy and base position 1 was selected outside of ISO-CUBE range, where the plate was moved on the X axis much more than the two other axes with slightly orientation changes. It shall be examined how the robot behaves inside and outside of ISO-CUBE range. The base positions were entered in *Fastsurf* to generate an offline robot program. The [8] thesis had extensively investigated the influence of override function on accuracy with a combination of PTP and LIN movement at 2 m/s velocity in automatic mode. For that autonomous application, 30% override with 2 m/s velocity is recommended. Furthermore, the author suggests more detailed analysis with a 100% override function and indicates other results for different applications. The author has also observed better absolute accuracy with 100% override and 0.6 m/s travelling speed. Therefore the offline robot program was generated with 0.8 m/s velocity and 100% override, to avoid override influence. With an LIN movement in teach-in mode, the robot was positioned above 550 mm in Z direction to respective base position. Thereafter, the actual $MSP_{reflector}$ position was measured with a laser tracker and compared with the target position, or rather with offline program data. Base position 1, which is outside of ISO-CUBE range, shows, especially in Z axis, a maximum of 1.597 mm deviation compared to -0.543 mm in base position 2. Also, the values 0.569 mm in X and 0.15 mm in Y direction of base position 2 shows that absolute accuracy decreases outside of ISO-CUBE range, or rather with the increasing distance from Rob-root. Both absolute and relative deviation in orientation is comparatively smaller than position deviation. But due to the working distance of camera TCP (in this case 550 mm), there is considerable optical leverage, which causes 0.547 mm position deviation for the maximum angle deviation of 0.057° (base 1 angle C). It must be noted that the deviation was measured in Spatial Analyser, where a best-fit transformation error for the creation of a common coordinate was 0.24. Furthermore, the deviation values will change with a different robot or additional external axes, as mentioned in the previous chapter. It is to be expected, that the deviation value will get worse, as the robot used for this experiment was a high precision robot without any external axis. Neither any other investigation nor any further improvement measures were carried out, as similar

results were also achieved in the preliminary investigation in [5]. Therefore further experiments were performed for geometric and hand-eye calibration. The results are published in paper [4].

Figure 2: MSP with thermography end-effector

2.2 Experimental setup for 3D thermography accuracy

Due to the lack of reference points and frayed component edges, it was difficult to perform an absolute accuracy analysis between two methods. For this reason, a component with sharp edges was selected for the new test and three reference points were chipped with a peening tool. For relative accuracy analysis between two 3D thermography methods, lines were drawn on the component's surface, which had a different thermal contrast than the component itself (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Drawn control lines on assembled component

In an ideal case, after image stitching, any offset should occur between two connected lines. Moreover, due to the small size of the component, the component should be placed somewhere within the robotic cell in order to investigate the influence of the specific reach of the robot. Thus the component was fixed on an additional plate with six target plates with reflectors, so that only base measurement is necessary for a new robot position. Normally a single base is measured for a component, no matter how large the component. Robot inaccuracy increases with the distance from the base. Since the component for this experiment was very small, and 3 new base positions were measured after the component was moved, the robot's absolute inaccuracy should be lower. After assembling the component, the positions of all six reflectors on target plates and three reference points (see Figure

4(b)) were measured with T-scan, and, the point cloud was generated with 0.1 mm point distance (see Figure 4(a)).

Figure 4: (a) Measured point clouds with T-SCAN; (b) Reference points and 3D Mesh generated from point clouds

Figure 5: (a) Three different base positions; (b) Experimental setup at base position one

From this point cloud a 3D Mesh with 0.5 mm vertex size, calibration data for laser projector and 3D corresponding points for 3D thermography were generated in Catia. Afterwards the component was placed in three different positions (see Figure 5 (a)) in the robotic cell. All bases were measured by the robot and a robot program was created with OLP for each base. Individual base measurement errors were for base one 0.25, base two 0.42 and for base three 0.35. The calibration error of the laser projector for this experiment was 0.12. The projecting distance was approx. 3.2 m. Base positions two and three were chosen such a way that the robot had to stretch to its maximum and the laser projector had to project by using its maximum opening angle. Base position one was in ISO-CUBE range. It was expected that the projecting error in the 3D model would be small in base one.

2.3 Results

In total 6 images were captured for each base position to measure the full component. All developed PnP methods and robot-based methods were applied to generate the 3D thermography model. 3D models which were generated only with the $PPnP$ and robot-based methods are illustrated in Figure 6.

Due to the higher component's curvature, any measurable deviation between the non-linear PnP and linear PnP method could be determined.

Figure 6: At base position 3: (a) 3D thermography model generated with $PPnP$ method; (b) 3D thermography model generated with robot-based method

On the other hand, a clear difference could be ascertained between the robot-based method and the PnP method. In this chapter, for example the $PPnP$ -based 3D model was analysed with the robot-based 3D model. While observing the robot-based model in Figure 7a, a non-collinear line between image positions 1 and 6 stands out. The lines are 1.56 mm apart at this position. On closer inspection in Figure 7c, a white border with a black spot becomes visible. Since the component structure does not change at this point, the thermal property should not change either. By comparison with the original image it becomes obvious that the white border and black spot do not belong to the component. The 3D model error at this edge lies between 1.21 mm and 1.54 mm. The same analysis with the $PPnP$ model (see Figure 8) shows no white border at this edge. The connected drawn line at the stitching position between images shows 0.12 mm average error for $PPnP$ method. In contrast the robot-based model is slightly better except for one position.

Figure 7: Enlarged robot-based 3D model

Figure 8: Enlarged PPnP based 3D model

A further absolute accuracy analysis was continued with reference points. Therefore both 3D models were superimposed with the reference points onto the *Catia* model. Here also a significant accuracy difference between the two methods could be recognised. Depending on the base position and reference point, a minimum of 0.36 mm and maximum of 0.805 mm positioning error was recognised for the PPnP method. The error for the robot-based method was much higher. The minimum and maximum errors were 1.307 mm and 2.067 mm respectively. In Figure 9 and Figure 10 the results are illustrated. The selected white points in these figures are constructed reference points and the centre of bright spots (marked as white circle) thermal image represents the same reference points. Due to chipping at these reference points the thermal property is different from the neighbouring surface area. It should be noted that the selection of the middle point of this bright spot was manual. This may lead to varying of the error number a little. Despite of these measurement limitations, it could be shown that the PnP-based method achieved better accuracy. Due to the extraordinarily small 3D mapping error, it is difficult to distinguish the chain of error, as in paper [4] where an average 0.13° , TCP tilt angle error was registered along with the robot's absolute inaccuracy.

Figure 9: (a) At reference point 1 and base position 3; (b) At reference point 2 and base position 2

Figure 10: (a) At reference point 2 and base position 2; (b) At reference point 3 and base position 3

3 Conclusions

In this series of tests, the most important elements of the error chain were analysed, especially for the robot-based method. In addition to the absolute robot accuracy investigation in 6D, the influences of geometric and hand-eye calibration could be determined. Since both the absolute robot accuracy and TCP inaccuracy in all three directions and orientations affect the total error of 1.3 mm for the robot-based method, it was difficult to separate the absolute error contribution for each influence. Especially when it comes to TCP determination, it can be said that a better approach or measuring equipment is needed to determine the minor difference, which is in less than one mm range. Although the robot-based method in this test series had achieved the minimum accuracy of 1.307 mm, it can be improved by already recognisable optimisation potentials such as using a laser-tracker-based absolute robot position while determining the TCP. Thus a doubling of the accuracy is conceivable. This kind of external-sensor-based TCP determination needs to be done only once and does not affect robot-based thermography measurement. The PnP-based method has achieved 0.3 mm minimum accuracy and can be used without hesitation for automated processes.

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